

USE OF COOPERATIVE EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGIES IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE IN "TEMURBEKLAR MAKTABI" STUDENTS

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Abstract. The article shows the main features and criteria of using collaborative learning technologies in the development of communicative competence in the students of "Temurbek School". Also, the mechanisms of the application of cooperative educational technologies in the process of teaching English and teacher-student relations are revealed. Pedagogical conditions for the development of communicative competence in students through English language learning are justified.

Key words: competence, communicative competence, teaching technologies, cooperative teaching, cooperative work, communication skills, communicative competences.

Аннотация. В статье показаны основные особенности и критерии использования технологий коллаборативного обучения в развитии коммуникативной компетенции у учащихся «Школы Темурбек». Также раскрываются механизмы применения кооперативных образовательных технологий в процессе обучения английскому языку и в отношении «учитель-ученик». Обоснованы педагогические условия развития коммуникативной компетентности учащихся посредством изучения английского языка.

Ключевые слова: компетентность, коммуникативная компетентность, технологии обучения, кооперативное обучение, совместная работа, коммуникативные навыки, коммуникативные компетенции.

In a modern foreign school, there are many different programs for the development of social skills, personal growth, communicative competence and behavioral strategies. Since the 1980s, most American schools have introduced courses in rhetoric and communication in order to develop the culture of verbal and non-verbal expression in students, to develop tolerance, and to teach them to deal with interpersonal conflicts and conflicts without violence [5]. These goals are served by the widespread use of the "collaborative learning" method, which forms a culture of equal partner interaction, group search and decision-making in the university and school [3].

The current state of society's information resources, the acceleration of their replenishment and renewal, the transition to new information resources, educational standards lead to a revision of both methodological positions and technological solutions. In this regard, it is necessary to optimize the educational process for learning English at school, to ensure effective and high-quality teaching of children's communication in English [2].

Psychological-pedagogical conditions to ensure the effectiveness of the English language teaching process are based on its principles: person-oriented education, in the educational process, collective interaction, concentration in the organization of educational material and educational process, multifunctionality of exercises and role-based organization, etc. All of the above principles of activation of the English language teaching process ensure a clear connection between the learning material and learning activities and help to effectively implement learning goals. Thus, the learning process includes:

1) to achieve certain different goals of teaching English for different contingents of students based on teaching conditions (number of teaching hours, timetable, number of students in a teaching group, formation of a training course); special learning area). 2) using psychological knowledge, person-oriented and competency-based approaches.

Cooperative learning is a person-centered approach technology in teaching English. It involves organizing groups of students who work together to solve a topic, problem, or question.

There are several options for collaborative learning technology. Studying the student body. This option focuses on "team goals" and the success of the whole group (team success), which can only be achieved as a result of the independent work of each team member in constant contact with other members of the same group. topic or problem. It is based on three main principles of student team learning:

a) "rewards" - groups receive one by one in the form of a score, some distinction, certificate, praise or other type of evaluation of their joint activity. Teams do not compete with each other, because they have different levels and goals, as well as time to achieve the goal; b) the "individual" or "personal" responsibility of each student indicates that the success or failure of the whole team depends on the success or failure of each of its members. It is an equal opportunity for everyone to monitor the progress of each other, the whole team, and progress in understanding and mastering the material. This means that the student brings points to his team, which he earns by improving his previous results. For the

interaction of students in groups, it is very important to evaluate the efforts of the weak student to achieve the desired results, not the actual results. For example, a strong student should complete 10 tasks, an average student 8, and a weak student 6 to get an "excellent" score. The obtained points are summed up and the average score is set for the group. for this test. The main principle of this technology is to take responsibility for yourself and encourage friends to help; The method of organizing cooperative education (cooperative education) was developed by Professor Eliot Aronson in 1978 and translated literally from English - called open saw, machine saw. In practice, in pedagogy, this option is shortened to "saw". Here, students are divided into groups of 4-6 people to work on the learning material, which in turn are divided into sections (semantic or logical blocks). It is advisable to organize this work at the stage of creative application of language material. Each team member searches for material for his or her part of the assignment. Then all students working on the same question, but in different groups, meet as experts on the issue and share what they have found. This is called an "expert meeting". Then, returning to their groups, they teach the other team members what they have learned. They, in turn, indicate their part of the task (like the teeth of a saw). Students are encouraged to observe their peers' conscientious completion of assignments, as this may affect their overall final grade. Each individual and the entire team reports on the entire topic. At the final stage, it is carried out frontally, the teacher can ask any student of the group to answer a question on this topic. A group of students have the right to complete their friends' answers as they wish. Additions to the answers are taken into account in the general test [5].

R. In 1986, Slavin developed a version of this method called "Jigsaw-2" (Jigsaw-2), which allowed students to work in groups of 4-5 people. Instead of each member of the group taking a separate part of the overall work, the whole team worked on the same material (for example, reading the main text on the topic "Travel" in print or aloud). At the same time, each member of the group will have his own sub-topic, which he will carefully study and become an expert on. Meetings of experts of various groups are ongoing. At the end of the lesson, all students passed the control exam, which was graded. The results of the students were summarized. The team with the highest total score received a prize or prize.

Another type of collaborative learning was developed at the University of Minnesota in 1987 (David Johnson, Roger Johnson). The class is divided into homogeneous (according to the level of training) groups of 3-4 people. Each

group gets one assignment, which is a small part of a larger topic that the whole class is working on. For example, the whole class is working on the same topic "Travel". All together plan the route and type of trip. Each group is given the task of preparing its part: ordering tickets for the whole group, hotel; development of a program for a group of tourists or an official delegation to be at the final point of the route; luggage preparation etc.

As a result of the joint work of individual groups and all groups in general, mastering of all materials is achieved. In the process of work, groups communicate with each other in the process of collective discussion, clarify details, offer their options, ask each other questions.

According to the developers of this method, great attention should be paid by the teacher to filling groups (taking into account the individual and psychological characteristics of each member) and developing tasks for each specific group. Within the group, the students themselves determine the roles of each member of the group in performing a common task and in organizing the successful and coordinated work of the whole group: observing the activity of each member of the group in solving the problem, the common task, the culture of communication within the group; determination of intermediate and final results; registering these results, editing them, etc. Thus, from the beginning, the group, as it were, performs a double task: on the one hand, academic - to achieve some cognitive, creative goal, and on the other, social-psychological - to realize the goal. a certain culture of communication in the performance of the task.

The main principles of cooperative learning are as follows:

- 1) interdependence of group members;
- 2) individual responsibility of each member of the group for their success and the success of their comrades;
- 3) joint educational, cognitive, creative and other activities of students in a group;
- 4) socialization of students' activities in groups;
- 5) general assessment of group work (descriptive plan, not always with points), which consists of evaluating the form of communication, students in the group, along with the scientific results of the work. In the classroom, all children are different: some understand quickly, others take a long time to understand, it is difficult for them, they become isolated and soon find themselves completely specialized in English from the educational process. If you group children into small groups of 3-4 people and give them one common task, defining the role of each in the performance of this task, a situation arises where the student is

responsible not only for his work, but also for the result of his work. The formation of groups is carried out in such a way that there are both "strong" students and "weak" students in each group.

The "weak" try to learn from the "strong" questions that they don't understand, while the "strong" are interested in making sure that all members of the group thoroughly understand the material. In this way, the spaces are connected to each other. In addition, students' self-learning and mutual learning takes place during group work. Independent education is carried out during the student's independent study of a part of the subject, mutual education - in the process of exchange of received information. It should also be noted that teamwork helps to form collective and community as a moral quality [6].

Tasks involving cooperative learning can be of different nature: checking homework, working on a text for reading, preparing for a text or test, working together on a project, working on spelling skills, working with vocabulary, etc. After determining the learning objectives of the lesson, it is important to determine what roles the students' work in groups will provide. It should be clear to the students and they will decide for themselves who is able to fulfill which role.

A person-centered approach in the context of the classroom system is one possible way of doing it. The teacher occupies a new, no less important role for the educational process - the role of the organizer of independent educational, cognitive, communicative and creative activities of students. It has more opportunities for differentiating the learning process, interpersonal communication opportunities, improving students' speech skills in the process of joint activity. At the same time, unlike other teaching technologies, the teacher is a full participant in the learning process. This method of teaching emphasizes "group goals" and the success of the whole group, which can only be achieved by working independently in constant contact with other members of the same group as each member of the group works on the subject being taught. Our work and observations in this direction have shown that the group form of organizing educational work has a number of advantages:

- helps to increase learning motivation, - teaches to evaluate oneself and others objectively, - increases the student's business status in the team, makes the lesson colorful. Working in a group, students demonstrate verbal independence. They help each other, successfully correct the thoughts of the interlocutors, even if they are not given such a task. In order for group speech cooperation to be effective, it is necessary to purposefully teach communication technologies to

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schoolchildren, clearly following the basic principles of cooperative learning. Practice has shown that the most successful groups are those whose members complement each other: one is effective, but not emotional; the second has personal experience, but not success; the third knows little, but is interested in this matter.

A sense of cooperation and mutual support appears in the work process. In this work, the ability of students to evaluate their own work is very important, so one of the points on the evaluation sheet is self-evaluation. In our opinion, this final stage of the lesson allows each student to analyze not only the work of his peers, but also his own. It is necessary to approach the goal gradually and patiently in order to implement and use the cooperative organization of teaching, to involve each student in active learning activities and to pay attention to teaching communication culture:

- communicate in a group with any partner or partners; - taking the given task seriously and working actively; - communicating with partners with sincerity and courtesy; - feeling a sense of responsibility not only for their own success, but also for the success of their partners and the whole class; - full understanding that teamwork in groups is serious and responsible work [1].

All the listed features of cooperative learning technology correspond to the methodological basis of the systematic-activity approach.

In conclusion, we note that the experience and observations on this issue help to increase the efficiency of the formation of communicative competence, because it increases the motivation of students and ensures the effectiveness of their educational work.

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